

SOME ASPECTS OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS THROUGH THE ISSUE OF GREEN BONDS

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Abstract. In this article, the issue of green bonds, which is considered the most common type of green financial instruments in attracting investments to the country, and its necessity and importance, are highlighted.

Key words: Investment attraction, sources of financing investment projects, green bonds, GREEN BONDS, financial instrument.

Relevance of the topic. Today, the process of attracting investments to various sectors of the economy has become an urgent issue. However, with the change of times and times, the negative complications of investments that may affect nature and the environment, whether they are the most developed countries or developing countries, are definitely being studied. That is, it is necessary to create such financial mechanisms or instruments, which will provide the opportunity to preserve the global climate and leave mother nature with all its elements to the next generation.

As a proof of the above points, the United Nations began to use various terms and terms from the 80s of the last XX century, including the goals of sustainable development - this is the way of life of all mankind by improving the economic, social and environmental situation of the United Nations in the world. is a global call aimed at improving and improving living conditions, building a fair and stable society. Since the experience of different countries in the field of sustainable development is very different, all the goals and related tasks of the 2030 Agenda are formulated in a general, universal form and, as a rule, there are no specific quantitative goals. It is determined that each country will localize the BRM, that is, develop national development goals based on its development priorities and financial capabilities from the 169 tasks of the 2030 agenda.

Analysis and results

At the same time, countries are using a new term, i.e. the economic category of GREEN BONDS, to attract investments through the stock market. So what is this financial instrument and what can it offer? - question is considered important.

Green bonds are debt securities issued to attract investments in projects aimed at improving the environmental situation or at least minimizing damage to nature. Proceeds from the bond issue will be used to implement green projects that must be properly described in the bond issue documents. All specified green projects must provide environmental benefits, provided that they are evaluated by the issuer in terms of qualitative and, if possible, quantitative characteristics [1].

The principles of issuing green bonds are presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Principles of investment attraction through green bonds [2]

The principles outlined in Figure 1 above clearly provide several broad categories of green projects that contribute to environmental goals.

The net proceeds from the placement of green bonds or an amount equal to these net proceeds must be transferred to a separate account kept in a separate portfolio or separately accounted for by the issuer. The calculation method should be determined by the issuer in the form of a separate internal procedure related to the implementation of credit and investment operations in relation to green projects.

The emergence of the green bond market is generally considered to be 2007, when the European Investment Bank issued \$600 million worth of Climate Awareness Bonds - these bonds were used to finance alternative energy development projects. Although the term “green bond” itself had not yet been coined, it was the first issue of securities to raise funds exclusively for environmental initiatives, specifically climate bonds that combat severe climate change.

In 2008, Green Bonds, already officially named, were issued by the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD). The collected funds were used to finance projects that were independently evaluated by experts from the University of Oslo. This is the first time specific environmental criteria have been applied that test projects for their commitment to sustainable development goals. Although a number of countries had issued bonds to finance environmental projects before 2007, the new approach was to tie bond issuance strictly to specific areas of spending.

As a new financial instrument in the Republic of Uzbekistan, for the first time in 2023 green sovereign international bonds in the amount of 4.25 trillion soums and international bonds in the amount of 660 million dollars were placed on the London Stock Exchange.

The financial resources attracted by these green financial instruments are aimed at introducing water-saving technologies, developing railway transport and metro transport, organizing sanitation works and ensuring cleanliness in settlements, wind erosion and sand inundation of water management facilities. will be channeled to finance green projects such as planting counter-environment trees. The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) was involved in the selection process of such projects. “Sustainalytics” received a second-party positive opinion on the green bond program.

Suggestions and recommendations

The green bond market in our country has a relatively short history, but it can be seen that the popularity of this tool is growing rapidly every year, which confirms

its great potential. Green bonds attract a wide range of socially responsible investors who aim to have a positive impact on the environment. In this regard, we believe that it is necessary to formulate some recommendations for the development of the sector, that is, first of all, to increase tax incentives as an incentive for business entities that want to issue a green financial instrument (at least 50% of the saved funds should be used for environmental protection with the condition of directing to improvement), and secondly, issues such as the long-term exemption of investors who direct their capital to green debt financial instruments from various mandatory fees and income tax.

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